

RESEARCH LIBRARIES, RESEARCHERS & THE EOSC: HOW DO THEY INTERACT?

Southern European Landscape, 18 January 2021 (14:30 - 16:15 CET)

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Introduction

The workshop held on 18 January 2021 was the first in a series of five workshops organized by Scientific Knowledge Services (SKS) and LIBER with the aim of answering the following questions:

- 1) What is the value of EOSC for researchers and research libraries, based on the goals/work of the EOSC?
- 2) What is the input needed from these stakeholders toward the EOSC?
- 3) How can these stakeholder groups be actively involved in EOSC activities and what do they need to get involved?
- 4) What feedback mechanism could be built to continuously inform EOSC, in its quest to remain an agile infrastructure?

This first workshop focused on the Southern European landscape. The target audience were researchers and research library staff, and the number of participants (excluding organisers, presenters, the moderator and the rapporteur) was 33 (22 female participants, 10 male participants and one participant that registered under his/her institution's name). The participants were from 13 countries: Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Italy, Lithuania, Moldova, the Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Spain and Turkey¹.

The workshop's agenda included three 10-minute presentations by invited speakers, three simultaneous breakout sessions (discussion groups), the discussion groups' presentations and

¹ Participants from Romania (6 part.) and Lithuania (1 part.) attended between 10 - 90 minutes of the workshop, depending on the participant, but in general less than 60.

the closing remarks by the workshop’s moderator, Liisi Lembinen, the Development Director at the University of Tartu Library.

Presentations

1 Eva Méndez: *EOSC and the challenge of interdisciplinary research (when the F of Findable, become a D of Discoverable).*

Dr Méndez made metadata the focus of her presentation, drawing on the work she’s been doing with the [FAIRsFAIR project](#).

Figure 1: The challenges of interdisciplinary research (Denkschets, 2021)

She distinguishes between three layers of the EOSC: the data layer (the foundation), which includes libraries and their work with metadata, particularly in the context of repositories; the service layer in the middle and the governance layer on the top.

Challenges for the metadata in the context of the EOSC include providing good metadata while avoiding the “my own standard is the one that I want to use” approach; namely, each discipline comes with its own metadata and this heterogeneity is a big issue, which needs to be addressed. This especially affects university libraries. Another issue is the need for quality metadata.

FAIRsFAIR is trying to address these problems through five big European projects (five [ESFRI clusters](#)) that represent five big domains (astronomy and physics, life sciences, environmental sciences, photon and neutron, humanities). Their aim is to apply FAIR principles to their research infrastructures, connecting them to the EOSC. **What’s being created is a metadata layer that cuts horizontally across the previously mentioned data layer with a task to make cross-disciplinary metadata catalogues for a better FAIR uptake, making data not only findable and interoperable, but also discoverable.**

2 Biljana Kosanović and Milica Ševkušić: *What do Southern-Eastern Europe (SEE) librarians know about EOSC and FAIR data? Not enough.*

Biljana Kosanović presented some of the results of the landscape survey conducted within the NI4OS-Europe project. The survey showed that **librarians in SE Europe do not have enough knowledge about the EOSC yet**. One of the solutions is introducing the topics of Open Science into the LIS university curricula. However, Ms Kosanović sees the **move towards Open Science as an opportunity for librarians - if given the adequate training - to become the (key) stakeholders in the process of adopting Open Science and promoting the EOSC.**

Figure 2: Data stewardship within libraries (Denkschets, 2021)

The co-presenter, Milica Ševkušić, shifted the focus of the presentation from the regional landscape to the situation in Serbia, speaking with passion and urgency. **The problems in Serbia include a rather low familiarity with the RDM and FAIR among both librarian and research communities, lack of institutional support from e.g. university libraries and an outdated LIS curriculum.**

One participant had **a question about the role of data stewardship within the libraries**, wondering if this role could be supported by librarians, and how they could work together. Milica welcomed the idea of introducing data stewards, who possess discipline-specific knowledge that librarians don't have, into every organization, especially for dealing with data management and data processing, but also remarks that it is not realistic for this to happen in Serbia any time soon.

3 Pedro Principe: *The Role of libraries in EOSC: powering Open and FAIR science and offering trusted services*

Pedro Principe sees **academic and research libraries as the key to implementation of Open Science practices and FAIR data within the EOSC development**. According to him, these are the **three main roles** of academic and research libraries in the EOSC:

1. **Libraries as content providers, ensuring the “O” of the “EOSC”**. **Institutional and thematic repositories, data archives and other research products repositories managed by libraries should be part of the main content provided for the EOSC**. However, libraries need to focus more on interoperability and its different components, such as metadata, PIDs, etc. They also need to invest more into supporting self-archiving services or practices of research software, and ensure access to other sorts of research outputs, not only publications.
2. **Libraries as service providers for the EOSC** - there is one specific service that libraries should focus on, and that's training. **Libraries need to be an active part of training infrastructure to support the EOSC and connect it to its end users**. This includes Open Access, Open Data, RDM and FAIR data training programs and resources. The challenge awaiting libraries is to contribute to building the EOSC training catalog/platform that will be developed in the upcoming period.
3. **Libraries as active players in the development of national infrastructures - **another critical aspect in the development of the EOSC are the ways in which libraries can actively participate on a national level in the implementation of the EOSC, synchronization of EOSC services and infrastructures, development of national research infrastructures and Open Science and FAIR policies****. However, not all librarians are familiar with these ideas and concepts. Libraries should also focus on FAIR data certification of repositories and services.

Breakout sessions

After the presentations, the participants – divided into three groups – discussed the four questions listed in the introductory part of this report, and noted their comments using the

Google application called Jamboard. A relatively small number of participants in each room was a good idea because it left each enough room to speak. Unfortunately, not all of them used this opportunity and **there was a certain reluctance to speak in general**, which moderators managed to deal with to a certain extent. **Although the participants expressed their genuine views and concerns, the unique rhythm and course of each session was definitely set by the moderators.** In all three workshops, there were only 2-3 cases of participants referring back to the speakers' contributions.

Each discussion was very different in style from the other two and this was reflected in their summaries and eventually in this report.

In one of the sessions, for example, the participants left many notes with many very interesting ideas, but they did that silently. Not enough time was allocated to more detailed elaboration of these comments. This resulted in the lack of context, so the comments on the Jamboard had to be reported as they are.

Another session focused more on the issues different from the ones highlighted by the four questions.

In general, participants in all three sessions showed interest, but not all of them voiced their opinions/experiences. For example, one could get an excellent picture about the situation in Serbia, learn something about the situation in Greece, Italy and Portugal, but almost nothing about the situation in e.g. Croatia. However, the participants that joined the discussion actively, expressed their wishes, hopes and concerns rather clearly, either in speech or through the notes. **The overall feeling is that the librarians welcome the EOSC and want to see themselves as a stakeholder in that project, but are still very much unsure about how this wish will be turned into reality. This is even more true for the researchers.**

Here is the summary of the breakout session discussions, highlighting in yellow some important ideas (one should not limit the attention only to those highlights):

QUESTION 1 What is the value of EOSC for researchers and research libraries, based on the goals/work of the EOSC?

- It was stated that there are differences in the level of involvement with the EOSC, not just from one country to another, but also between the libraries in the same country.
- There is a general agreement between the participants in the discussions that – at least in Southern and Eastern Europe – there is very little knowledge of the EOSC among both

the librarians and researchers. Many librarians are not quite sure yet what exactly the EOSC is. One of them described the concept as “quite complex” and “a bit confusing”.

- There is hope that the EOSC would provide a good and easy tool to solve certain data management problems that libraries cannot solve by themselves, or that cannot be solved on a local/national level. There is a fear that otherwise a huge amount of research data pouring into understaffed (and sometimes under skilled) libraries might get lost.
- The EOSC was described as “a meta-catalogue of metadata”, a system that will facilitate discoverability of the data from institutions’ repositories on the global level.
- The EOSC is seen as the place where research data can be shared with a standardization of metadata.
- The EOSC could provide libraries with an opportunity to take stronger positions within their institutions as supporters in data discovery and RDM, with librarians evolving to data science support for the long tail research.
- However, there is also a fear that there is no place for libraries in the EOSC except as content and training providers. Eva Mendez partly agreed on this one, emphasizing that the EOSC is a very complex and high-level infrastructure and that many libraries will not have staff competent enough (she mentions data stewards) to deal with it; it goes beyond repositories. She wouldn’t say there is no place for libraries, but there is no clearly defined place yet.
- In a specific case of Serbia (and possibly in some other countries in this landscape, too), there is a lack of knowledge about Open Science among the funders. They need to be educated about what to ask from researchers regarding the questions of Open Science in the calls for projects.
- The librarians also see the value of the EOSC in the promotion of library services and librarian profession (once they have been adequately trained).
- For researchers, the EOSC could be a place to find reliable data (EOSC = the information authority) they can use in their research, and also hopefully the place where they might discover unexpected data that could enrich their research.
- However, there is a strong feeling that researchers need to be persuaded more convincingly and clearly about the value of the EOSC in order to accept it as something more than just another system they need to master.
- The EOSC could be the place to offer **Service Level Agreement** for data and other research artefacts.
- It might serve as a framework for developing interoperability standards, and a place which offers sustainability in the research process.

QUESTION 2 What is the input needed from these stakeholders towards the EOSC?

- Libraries know the real needs of their end-users, and they have a very important support role as mediators of these needs towards the EOSC - they could help in

translating the EOSC into local and national settings and vice versa, providing advice to both the EOSC (on the services needed) and researchers and local infrastructures (supporting their engagement with the EOSC).

- Libraries will provide data and standardized metadata to the EOSC. They will need to work with researchers to find the best way to share their data, and both librarians and researchers need more leadership from the EOSC architects in this respect.
- There is also a belief that libraries will have a role in supporting the projects in the long tail of science, which are happening outside well-structured research infrastructures, by ensuring that important data from small projects, PhD projects etc. become part of the EOSC, too.
- Libraries should also serve as service providers: one of their main roles should be providing training for the EOSC, to librarians and researchers.
- Astrid Verheusen from LIBER posed the question of the way in which librarians communicate Open Science in general to the researchers: do they speak the language of researchers? Do they have necessary soft skills? In response to this, Milica talked about her own experience being the EOSC promotor. She breaks down the concept of Open Science and the EOSC into many smaller topics (e.g. RDM, open access, FAIR...) and then deals with each of them separately. She found out this is the only way to make this topic understandable to the researchers.
- There is a suggestion for setting up a working group for research libraries to analyze task conversions.
- The opinion was heard that this input will depend on the librarians, on how much they would like to be involved in Open Science. Some libraries still offer quite old-fashioned services to the end-users, and now is the opportunity to change this.
- As for researchers, they should make a commitment to share the data (both those that work and those that don't work).
- EOSC Association to showcase for a bigger budget – cloud services are expensive

QUESTION 3 How can these stakeholder groups be actively involved in EOSC activities and what do they need to get involved?

The following ideas were heard:

Libraries

- an EOSC Stakeholder Forum, including a free online version – useful for quick updates and news sharing
- a national stakeholder forum with participation from the EOSC country representatives-
- a national EOSC country representative involved in all the EOSC related events and meetings in the country
- webinars

- a specific event, e.g. a workshop, for the stakeholders that do not know much about the EOSC yet
- “EOSC for dummies” – a guide that will help the potential stakeholders get the clear idea of what the EOSC is
- competence centers as places where libraries will both receive and provide training
- some European infrastructures and groups are already actively involved in preparation for the EOSC (CESSDA, OPERAS, DARIAH, RDA), and there is place for libraries to work with them
- a working group for libraries, similar to the ones in RDA e.g. an EOSC Libraries Working Group
- formal partnerships with relevant library associations
- training for Open Science and the EOSC that would end in certification - this idea was welcomed enthusiastically by other participants as certificates contribute to career advancement
- involvement into local/national EOSC-related projects (also important in terms of budget)

Researchers

- more training of all sorts, including for example short video tutorials for different aspects of the EOSC
- promotion of the EOSC and its benefits, including rewards and incentives to motivate researchers to take Open Science more seriously
- adding a new criterion when evaluating/assessing research: “EOSC support activities”
- “the EOSC should step up in triggering intercontinental reciprocity to win the hearts and minds of the researchers from international projects”

QUESTION 4 What feedback mechanism could be built to continuously inform EOSC, in its quest to remain an agile infrastructure?

Commenting generally on this question, the question was asked as to whom exactly in the EOSC (the Commission, the clusters, ...?) libraries and researchers should communicate their questions.

Suggested ideas:

- a free online EOSC Symposium/Forum is a form of feedback
- national user groups
- a clear advocacy program
- EOSC Case Reports (similar to Clinical Case Reports)
- the EOSC working group in LIBER

- a system for different kinds of requests, e.g. reporting errors, requests for new functionalities etc.
- the EOSC help desk, but not the same one for the librarians and end-users; there should be a clear feedback mechanism for research support staff

There was also a plea not to create a new communication channel but to use the existing ones, e.g. RDA4Lib.

Additional comments and suggestions in the chat:

1. Eva Mendez suggested that the next workshop should include the topic of barriers to effective development of the EOSC.
2. Iulianna van der Lek-Ciudin from CLARIN ERIC shared in the chat the information about and the link to their [Knowledge centre for librarians](#). She added that they collaborate with librarians in the Europeana projects and that national libraries are active in many of the CLARIN national consortia.

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